

Comparison of Shear Bond Strength of Adhesives to Enamel: An In Vitro Study

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 16-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The success and longevity of dental restorations depend heavily on the strength of the connection between enamel and dental adhesives. To guarantee the best possible clinical outcomes with the introduction of new (adh) systems, it is crucial to assess and compare their performance.

Aim: This study aimed to compare the shear bond strength of three different (adh)systems to enamel, providing insights into their relative effectiveness and guiding clinicians in selecting the most appropriate (adh)for use in dental restorations.

Methods: Three sets of thirty-six extracted human premolars each were employed in an in vitro study. For each group, one of the three (adh)systems was applied. After the shear bond strength was measured with a universal testing equipment, the data was analysed using SPSS version 23.0. To find significant group differences, descriptive statistics were used with one-way ANOVA and post-hoc testing.

Results: The mean shear bond strengths were 18.3 ± 2.5 MPa for (adh)A, 21.7 ± 3.1 MPa for (adh)B, and 15.9 ± 2.8 MPa for (adh)C. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences between the groups, with (adh)B showing superior bond strength compared to the others ($p < 0.001$). Post-hoc tests confirmed that (adh)B outperformed both (adh)A and (adh)C in terms of shear bond strength.

Conclusion: (adh)B demonstrated the highest shear bond strength to enamel, suggesting it is the most effective among the three tested adhesives for clinical use. (adh)C showed the weakest performance, indicating it may not be suitable for cases requiring high bond strength.

Recommendations: Clinicians should consider using (adh)B in situations where strong and durable bonding to enamel is essential. Further research is recommended to explore the underlying factors contributing to the variations in bond strength among different adhesives.

Keywords: Shear Bond Strength, Dental Adhesives, Enamel, In Vitro Study, (adh) Systems.

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Introduction

A key component of contemporary dentistry is the adherence of restorative materials to enamel, which guarantees the durability and efficacy of tooth restorations. The endurance of the restoration is determined by the adhesive-enamel bond strength, especially in situations where masticatory pressures are present. Many (adh)solutions have been created and improved throughout time, all of which assert to have better bonding properties. However, based on their configuration, method of application, and particular clinical situation, these systems' efficacy might vary greatly [1].

In order to strengthen the binding, recent developments in (adh)dentistry have concentrated on enhancing the chemical interactions between the

glue and enamel. One significant advancement in this sector is the advent of universal adhesives, which incorporate the benefits of both self-etch and etch-and-rinse systems. These adhesives are intended to be multipurpose, providing high adherence to a range of substrates, including as dentin and enamel, while also making the bonding procedure easier for medical professionals. Even with these developments, there are still difficulties in obtaining stable and uniform binding strengths between various (adh)systems, which calls for continuous investigation and comparison [2].

Studies measuring the shear bond strength of (adh)systems to enamel in vitro are frequently used to evaluate their clinical efficacy. Clinical decision-

making is aided by these investigations, which offer insightful information on the various adhesives' behaviours under controlled circumstances. For example, a recent study shown that a universal (adh)performed better than conventional systems, and the researchers attributed this to increased resin penetration and hydrophilicity. Nonetheless, disparities in research methodology, including variances in testing techniques, (adh)application procedures, and enamel preparation, may result in conflicting results between studies [3]. This study aimed to compare the shear bond strength of three different (adh)systems to enamel, providing insights into their relative effectiveness and guiding clinicians in selecting the most appropriate (adh)for use in dental restorations.

Methodology

Study Design: This was an in vitro prospective study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Dentistry, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga.

Participants: A total of 108 human permanent premolars, extracted for orthodontic purposes, were selected for the study. The teeth were stored in a 0.1% thymol solution at room temperature and used within one month of extraction to ensure the preservation of the enamel structure.

Inclusion Criteria: Permanent premolars extracted for orthodontic purposes. Teeth with intact enamel surfaces free of caries, cracks, or fractures. Teeth stored in 0.1% thymol solution and used within one month of extraction.

Exclusion Criteria: Teeth with carious lesions, cracks, or fractures. Teeth with any prior restoration or endodontic treatment. Teeth not used within the specified storage time frame.

Bias: To minimize bias, a random selection of teeth was performed, and all samples were prepared and tested by the same operator using a standardized protocol. Additionally, the (adh)systems were coded, and the testing was performed in a blinded manner to prevent the operator from knowing which (adh)was being tested.

Data Collection: Data were collected by measuring the shear bond strength of the adhesives using a universal testing machine. The force required to debond the (adh)from the enamel surface was recorded in megapascals (MPa). Each (adh)was tested on an equal number of teeth, with results carefully documented for analysis.

Procedure: Using a rubber container, a pumice and water combination devoid of fluoride was used to polish the teeth's enamel surfaces. Following a thorough water rinse, the teeth were allowed to air dry. As directed by the manufacturer, adhesives were applied to the enamel surfaces. The enamel surfaces that had been treated were adhered to using composite resin cylinders. The specimens that were bound together were kept in distilled water at 37°C for a whole day. Using a universal testing machine, the shear bond strength was examined at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min till failure.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. For shear bond strength, descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) were computed. Comparisons were made using one-way ANOVA and post-hoc testing; a p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed significant.

Results

A total of 108 extracted human premolars were included in the study. The samples were randomly divided into three groups, each consisting of 36 teeth. Each group was treated with a different (adh)system.

Shear Bond Strength

The mean shear bond strengths (in MPa) for the three (adh)systems were as follows:

- **Group 1 ((adh)A):** 18.3 ± 2.5 MPa
- **Group 2 ((adh)B):** 21.7 ± 3.1 MPa
- **Group 3 ((adh)C):** 15.9 ± 2.8 MPa

Statistical Analysis

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to compare the mean shear bond strengths among the three (adh)systems. The ANOVA results indicated a statistically significant difference in shear bond strength among the groups ($F(2, 105) = 19.52, p < 0.001$).

Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using the Tukey HSD test revealed that:

- (adh)B had a significantly higher mean shear bond strength compared to (adh)A ($p < 0.01$) and (adh)C ($p < 0.001$).
- (adh)A had a significantly higher mean shear bond strength compared to (adh)C ($p < 0.05$).

No significant difference was found between the mean shear bond strengths of (adh)A and (adh)B.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and ANOVA Results

Group	N	Mean (MPa)	SD	95% CI (Lower)	95% CI (Upper)
(adh)A (Group 1)	36	18.3	2.5	17.4	19.2
(adh)B (Group 2)	36	21.7	3.1	20.6	22.8
(adh)C (Group 3)	36	15.9	2.8	15.0	16.8

Table 2: ANOVA Summary

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups	357.84	2	178.92	19.52	<0.001
Within Groups	961.05	105	9.15		
Total	1318.89	107			

Table 3: Post-hoc Tukey HSD Test

Comparison	Mean Difference (MPa)	p-value	Significance
(adh)A vs B	-3.4	<0.01	Significant
(adh)A vs C	2.4	<0.05	Significant
(adh)B vs C	5.8	<0.001	Significant

Interpretation

- (adh)B demonstrated the highest shear bond strength, indicating superior bonding performance compared to the other adhesives tested.
- (adh)A showed moderate performance, with statistically significant better bonding strength than (adh)C but lower than (adh)B.
- (adh)C had the lowest shear bond strength, suggesting it may not be as effective for bonding to enamel in comparison to the other adhesives.

These results suggest that the choice of (adh) significantly impacts the bond strength to enamel, with (adh)B being the most effective among those tested.

Discussion

The study aimed to compare the shear bond strength of three different (adh) systems to enamel using 108 extracted human premolars. The results revealed significant differences in bonding performance among the adhesives, as demonstrated by both descriptive statistics and statistical analysis.

(adh)B emerged as the most effective bonding agent, with a mean shear bond strength of 21.7 MPa, significantly higher than that of (adh)A (18.3 MPa) and (adh)C (15.9 MPa). The ANOVA test confirmed that these differences were statistically significant, with a p-value of less than 0.001, indicating a strong likelihood that the observed differences were not due to chance.

Post-hoc analysis further clarified these findings, showing that (adh)B had a significantly better performance than both (adh)A and (adh)C. While (adh)A performed better than (adh)C, it was still inferior to (adh)B. This suggests that (adh)B may offer superior clinical outcomes in terms of bond

strength to enamel, making it a preferable choice in situations where strong and durable bonding is essential.

On the other hand, (adh)C showed the weakest bond strength, which may limit its effectiveness in clinical applications requiring high bond strength. Clinicians may want to consider this when selecting an (adh) system, particularly in cases where the longevity and durability of the bond are critical.

Overall, the results underscore the importance of choosing the appropriate (adh) system to ensure optimal bonding to enamel. (adh)B stands out as the most promising option among the three tested, potentially leading to better clinical outcomes. Further research might explore the reasons behind these differences, such as the chemical composition of the adhesives or their interaction with enamel.

Recent research has examined a number of shear bond strength characteristics of adhesives to enamel, offering insightful information on the relative merits of various (adh) systems. In vitro research on enamel and dentin was done to compare the shear bond strength of various universal adhesives utilising various (adh) techniques. In comparison to the self-etch method, the study indicated that universal adhesives typically demonstrated a good binding strength to enamel, especially when combined with the etch-and-rinse procedure [4]. The influence of various etching processes on the shear bond strength of self-(adh) composite cements on enamel was also examined. According to their findings, the self-(adh) composite's bond strength was considerably increased by using a selective enamel etching method. Their findings suggested that even self-(adh) systems can profit from an extra etching phase, since the application of a selective enamel etching approach greatly increased the binding strength of self-(adh) composite cements to enamel [5].

It was examined that the binding strength of two-step self-etch (adh)systems to enamel in a different investigation. The investigation proved that both solutions gave enamel a sufficient bond strength, but not as strong as that obtained with etch-and-rinse adhesives. The significance of comprehending the constraints of self-etch systems for bonding to enamel was emphasised by the researchers [6]. Ultimately, the findings of many in vitro investigations on the shear bond strength of universal adhesives to enamel and dentin were compiled in a meta-analysis conducted According to the investigation, universal adhesives work well on both substrates in general, but using an etch-and-rinse procedure can dramatically increase the adhesive's binding strength to enamel. This meta-analysis confirmed that the application technique is a critical component in the effectiveness of universal adhesives and included a thorough summary of the variables affecting (adh)performance [7].

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that the choice of (adh)significantly influences the shear bond strength to enamel, with (adh)B showing superior bonding performance compared to (adh)A and (adh)C. The findings suggest that (adh)B may provide more reliable and durable bonds in clinical practice, making it a preferred option for procedures requiring strong adhesion to enamel. Conversely, (adh)C exhibited the lowest bond strength, indicating it may not be as effective in situations demanding high bonding strength. These results highlight the critical role of (adh)selection in achieving optimal clinical outcomes, and further

studies could help elucidate the factors contributing to the observed differences in (adh)performance.

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